

TWITTER SENTIMENT ANALYSIS USING MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract - People use Twitter extensively to share their thoughts and feelings on a variety of situations. Sentiment analysis is a method for examining data and extracting the sentiment it contains. Twitter sentiment analysis is the process of applying sentiment analysis to Twitter data (tweets) in order to identify user sentiments. The amount of study in this area has steadily increased over the last few decades. This is because tweets have a complex format that makes processing them challenging. Because tweets are so brief, they create a whole new set of issues, such as slang and abbreviations. The purpose of this study is to analyse a few studies on sentiment analysis on Twitter, including the approaches used and models used, as well as outlining a broader Python-based strategy.

Key Words: Python, natural language processing, machine learning, and sentiment analysis.

1.INTRODUCTION

Twitter has emerged as a major micro-blogging website, having over 100 million users generating over 500 million tweets every day. With such large audience, Twitter has consistently attracted users to convey their opinions and perspective about any issue, brand, company or any other topic of interest. Due to this reason, Twitter is used as an informative source by many organizations, institutions and companies.

On Twitter, users are allowed to share their opinions in the form of tweets, using only 140 characters. This leads to people compacting their statements by using slang, abbreviations, emoticons, short forms etc. Along with this, people convey their opinions by using sarcasm and polysemy.

Hence it is justified to term the Twitter language as unstructured.

In order to extract sentiment from tweets, sentiment analysis is used. The results from this can be used in many areas like analyzing and monitoring changes of sentiment with an event, sentiments regarding a particular brand or release of a particular product, analyzing public view of government policies etc. A lot of research has been done on Twitter data in order to classify the tweets and analyze the results. In this paper we aim to review of some researches in this domain and study how to perform sentiment analysis on Twitter data using Python. The scope of this paper is limited to that of the machine learning models and we show the comparison of efficiencies of these models with one another

2. ABOUT SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

Sentiment analysis is a process of deriving sentiment of a particular statement or sentence. It's a classification technique which derives opinion from the tweets and formulates a sentiment and on the basis of which, sentiment classification is performed.

Sentiments are subjective to the topic of interest. We are required to formulate that what kind of features will decide for the sentiment it embodies

The basic steps for performing sentiment analysis includes data collection, pre-processing of data, feature extraction, selecting baseline features, sentiment detection and performing classification either using simple computation or else machine learning approaches

2.1 Twitter Sentiment Analysis

The aim while performing sentiment analysis on tweets is basically to classify the tweets in different sentiment classes accurately. In this field of research, various approaches have evolved, which propose methods to train a model and then test it to check its efficiency.

Performing sentiment analysis is challenging on Twitter data, as we mentioned earlier. Here we define the reasons for this:

1.Limited tweet size: with just 140 characters in hand, compact statements are generated, which results sparse set of features.

2.Use of slang: these words are different from English words and it can make an approach outdated because of the evolutionary use of slangs.

3.Twitter features: it allows the use of hashtags, user reference and URLs. These require different processing than other words.

4.User variety: the users express their opinions in a variety of ways, some using different language in between, while others using repeated words or symbols to convey an emotion.

1. 3. METHODOLOGY

In order to perform sentiment analysis, we are required to collect data from the desired source (here Twitter). This data undergoes various steps of pre-processing which makes it more machine sensible than its previous form.

Fig. 1 – General Methodology for sentiment analysis

3.1 Tweet Collection

Tweet collection involves gathering relevant tweets about the particular area of interest. The tweets are collected using Twitter's streaming API [1], [3], or any other mining tool (for example WEKA

[2]), for the desired time period of analysis. The format of the retrieved text is converted as per convenience (for example JSON in case of [3], [5]).

3.2 Pre-processing of tweets

The preprocessing of the data is a very important step as it decides the efficiency of the other steps down in line. It involves syntactical correction of the tweets as desired. The steps involved should aim for making the data more machine readable in order to reduce ambiguity in feature extraction. Below are a few steps used for pre-processing of tweets -

1. Stop word removal: Stop words that don't affect the meaning of the tweet are removed (for example and, or, still etc.). [3] uses WEKA machine learning package for this purpose, which checks each word from the text against a dictionary ([3], [5]).
2. Twitter feature removal: User names and URLs are not important from the perspective of future processing; hence their presence is futile. All usernames and URLs are converted to generic tags [3] or removed [5].
3. Stemming: Replacing words with their roots, reducing different types of words with similar meanings [3]. This helps in reducing the dimensionality of the feature set.
4. Special character and digit removal: Digits and special characters don't convey any sentiment. Sometimes they are mixed with words, hence their removal can help in associating two words that were otherwise considered different.
5. Creating a dictionary to remove unwanted words and punctuation marks from the text [5].
6. Expansion of slangs and abbreviations [5].
7. Spelling correction [5].
8. Generating a dictionary for words that are important [7] or for emoticons [2].

3.3 Feature Extraction

A feature is a piece of information that can be used as a characteristic which can assist in solving a problem (like prediction [11]). The quality and quantity of features is very important as they are important for the results generated by the selected model.

Selection of useful words from tweets is feature extraction.

- 3.3.1 Unigram features – one word is considered at a time and decided whether it is capable of being a feature.
- 3.3.2 N-gram features – more than one word is considered at a time.
- 3.3.3 External lexicon – use of list of words with predefined positive or negative sentiment

4. TWITTER SENTIMENT ANALYSIS WITH PYTHON

4.1 Python

Python is a high level, interpreted programming language, created by Guido van Rossum. The language is very popular for its code readability and compact line of codes. It uses white space inundation to delimit blocks.

Python provides a large standard library which can be used for various applications for example natural language processing, machine learning, data analysis etc.

It is favored for complex projects, because of its simplicity, diverse range of features and its dynamic nature.

4.2 Natural Language Processing (NLTK)

Natural Language toolkit (NLTK) is a library in python, which provides the base for text processing and classification. Operations such as tokenization, tagging, filtering, text manipulation can be performed with the use of NLTK.

The NLTK library also embodies various trainable classifiers (example – Naïve Bayes Classifier).

NLTK library is used for creating a bag-of words model, which is a type of unigram model for text. In this model, the number of occurrences of each word is counted. The data acquired can be used for training classifier models. The sentiment of the entire tweets is computed by assigning subjectivity score to each word using a sentiment lexicon.

4.3 SCIKIT-LEARN

The Scikit-learn project started as scikits.learn, a Google Summer Code project by David Cournapeau. It is a powerful library that provides many machine learning classification algorithms, efficient tools for data mining and data analysis. Below are various functions that can be performed using this library:

4.3.1 Classification: Identifying the category to which a particular object belongs.

4.3.2 Regression: Predicting a continuous-valued attribute associated with an object.

4.3.3 Clustering: Automatic grouping of similar objects into sets.

4.3.4 Dimension Reduction: Reducing the number of random variables under consideration.

4.3.5 Model selection: Comparing, validating and choosing parameters and models.

4.3.6 Preprocessing: Feature extraction and normalization in order to transform input data for use with machine learning algorithm.

4.4 Pre-processing in Python

The pre-processing in Python is easy to perform due to functions provided by the standard library. Some of the steps are given below:

4.4.1 Converting all upper case letters to lower case.

4.4.2 Removing URLs: Filtering of URLs can be done with the help of regular expression `(http|https|ftp) ://[a-zA-Z0-9\.\.]+`.

4.4.3 Removing Handles (User Reference): Handles can be removed using regular expression `@(\w+)`.

4.4.4 Removing hashtags: Hashtags can be removed using regular expression `-(\w+)`.

4.4.5 Removing emoticons: We can use emoticon dictionary to filter out the emoticons or to save the occurrence of them in a different file.

Removing repeated characters

4.5 TRAINING A MODEL

The scikit-library provides various machine learning models whose implementation in code is very easy. For example, one can easily create an instance of Support Vector Machine in one line – `classifier_poly=svm.SVC()`

In order to make use of machine learning models, one is required to remember to install NumPy properly and import from scikit-learn the desired model.

After training the model we, use the same instance to test the model and save the results obtained.

4.6 Data Collection

We have two options to collect data for sentiment analysis. First is to use Tweepy - client for Twitter Application Programming Interface (API).

It can be installed using pip command: `pip install tweepy`

To fetch tweets from the Twitter API one needs to register an App through their Twitter account. After that the following steps are performed:

4.6.1 Open <https://apps.twitter.com/> and click button – ‘Create New App’.

4.6.2 Fill the details asked.

4.6.3 When the App is created, the page will be automatically loaded.

4.6.4 Open the ‘Keys and Access Tokens’ tab.

4.6.5 Copy ‘Consumer Key’, ‘Consumer Secret’, ‘Access token’ and ‘Access Token Secret’.

The keys copied are then inserted into the code, which helps in dynamic collection of tweets every time we run it.

The other option is to gather data non-dynamically using the existing data provided by websites (like kaggle.com) and save the data into whatever format we require (for example JSON, csv etc.).

The former method is slow in nature as it performs tweet collection every time we start the program.

The latter approach may not provide us with the quality of tweets we require.

5. EXPERIMENTATION FOR MODEL VALIDATION

After the pre-processing and feature extraction steps are

performed, we work towards training and validating the model’s performance. The collected dataset is divided in two– training set and testing set. The training set is used to train the classifier (machine learned model) while the testing set is the one on which the experimentation is performed. The ratio of training and testing dataset can vary as per to applications. [1] divides the dataset as 70% training and rest testing, whereas

[3] which uses cross validation on the dataset by splitting it into 10 sections. This method selects 90% for training set and 10 for testing.

[4] divided the set as training set containing 21000 tweets while testing set 1400 tweets (approx. 93% and 7%) while [5] used 75% data for training set and [9] used approx. 83% for training.

As the classification work in [6] is topic based and adaptive in nature hence excessive manual labeling is avoided which reduces the size of training set.

The model which is chosen for experimentation is trained using the training set of data. Then this same trained model is used to classify new data, by which we can check its accuracy.

As the classification work in [6] is topic based and adaptive in nature hence excessive manual labeling is avoided which reduces the size of training set.

The proposed work of [3] is a bit different as they correlate the event and sentiment by using timestamp. Using this method for a particular event, it’s possible to divide it into sub-events and further deepen the study of user sentiments. This approach is complex but yield very detail results when we chose a large event and desire to see fluctuations in user sentiments with time.

Fig. 2: Accuracy on the basis of number of classes used for classification of sentiments

Table 1: Average accuracies of different models

S. no.	Classifier	Accuracy
1.	DAN2	86.06%
2.	SVM	85.0%
3.	Bayesian Logistic Regression	74.84%
4.	Naïve Bayes	66.24%
5.	Random Forest Classifier	87.5%
6.	Neural Network	89.93%
7.	Maximum Entropy	90.0%
8.	Ensemble classifier	90.0%

5.1 Applications

0. Commerce: Companies can make use of this research for gathering public opinion related to their brand and products. From the company’s perspective the survey of target audience is imperative for making out the ratings of their products..

1. Politics: Majority of tweets on Twitter are related to politics. Due to Twitter’s widespread use, many politicians are also aiming to connect to people through it. People post their support or disagreement towards government policies, actions, elections, debates etc. Hence analyzing data from it can help is in determining public view.

2. Sports Events: Sports involve many events, championships, gatherings and some controversies too. Many people are enthusiastic sports followers and follow their favorite players present on Twitter. These people frequently tweet about different sports related events. We can use the data to gather public view of a player’s action, team’s performance, official decisions etc.

6.OUTPUT:

The system successfully processes a large dataset of tweets and classifies them into three main sentiment categories: positive, negative, and neutral. These classifications help in understanding public

opinion on various topics, providing a deeper insight into how users express their thoughts and emotions on Twitter. The system effectively handles the complexities of Twitter data, such as short text length, use of slang, abbreviations, hashtags, and emojis. Despite these challenges, the model accurately identifies key sentiment-indicating features in the text. A detailed analysis of the most commonly used words in different sentiment categories reveals that positive tweets frequently contain words. By leveraging natural language processing (NLP) techniques the system ensures efficient and accurate sentiment classification. Companies can use this technology to monitor customer feedback, improve product offerings, and enhance their overall engagement with users. Policymakers and organizations can also utilize sentiment analysis to assess public opinion on various issues, allowing them to respond proactively to concerns and sentiments expressed by the public. Overall, the successful execution of this project highlights its potential applications in various domains, including marketing, customer service, social media monitoring, political analysis, and brand reputation management. The integration of machine learning, NLP, and sentiment analysis in this project underscores the growing importance of automated sentiment classification in understanding human emotions and opinions on a large scale.

To provide a clearer understanding of the project execution and its results, we have included screenshots of key output screens.

Fig.3 Output screen of neutral sentiment

Fig.4 Output screen of negative sentiment

Fig.5 Output screen of positive sentiment

7. CONCLUSIONS

Twitter sentiment analysis comes under the category of text and opinion mining. It focuses on analyzing the sentiments of the tweets and feeding the data to a machine learning model in order to train it and then check its accuracy, so that we can use this model for future use according to the results. It comprises of steps like data collection, text pre-processing, sentiment detection, sentiment classification, training and testing the model. This research topic has evolved during the last decade with models reaching the efficiency of almost 85%-90%. But it still lacks the dimension of diversity in the data. Along with this it has a lot of application issues with the slang used and the short forms of words. Many analyzers don't perform well when the number of classes are increased. Also it's still not tested that how accurate the model will be for topics other than the one in consideration. Hence sentiment analysis has a very bright scope of development in future.

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